

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Part-IX. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(2-aryl-5*H*/methyl-4-thiazolidinon-3-ylmethoxy)diphenyl Sulphones

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Some new 4-thiazolidinone derivatives have been prepared bearing *p,p'*-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphone moiety. The Schiff bases from *p,p'*-bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone were condensed with thioglycolic and thiolactic acid and their structures established by ir and pmr spectral data. All the compounds show moderate antimicrobial activity.

4-Thiazolidinone derivatives are associated with diverse biological activities. Several reports have appeared in the literature, which highlight their chemistry and use¹. Agripat² reported that hydroxy-sulphones are well-known antibiotics, fungicides and bactericides. In continuation of our work on 4-thiazolidinone derivatives³, we have prepared some diaryl 4-thiazolidinone derivatives (4) with an intention to synthesise better therapeutic agents.

p,p'-Dihydroxydiphenyl sulphone was condensed with ethyl chloroacetate, which was treated with hydrazine hydrate to get *p,p'*-bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy) diphenyl sulphone (2). The hydrazide was then condensed with different aromatic aldehydes to give the Schiff bases (3). These on treatment with thioglycolic and thiolactic acid gave substituted-4-thiazolidinones (4) (Scheme 1). The structural assignment of the products was based on their ir and pmr spectral data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Spectral study: The compounds synthesised were scanned for their ir and pmr spectral study.

The ir spectrum of hydrazide (2) showed a characteristic bands at 3 300 (NH), 1 250 (C—O—C asym) and 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O). The ¹H nmr spectrum showed a sharp singlet at δ 4.32 (4H) which was assigned to the NH₂ protons, while the singlet at δ 4.6 (4H) could be due to ArOCH₂ protons. A multiplet at δ 8.0–6.96 is due to aromatic protons. A singlet in the downfield at δ 9.4 could be attributed to CONH protons.

The *p,p'*-bis(benzaldehydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (3) derivatives gave their bands at 1 650 (N=CH), 1 690 (C=O amide-I) and 1 250 cm⁻¹ (C—O—C asym.). The ¹H nmr spectrum for 3 revealed signals at δ 11.36 (2H, s) due to presence of CONH, exchangeable with D₂O. The singlet at δ 5.13 could be attributed to ArOCH₂ protons and a singlet at δ 4.65 to RCH=N proton. A

Scheme 1

multiplet at δ 8.17–6.75 was assigned to aromatic protons.

The thiazolidinone (4 ; R' = H) gave the characteristic ir bands at 1 240 (C—O—C asym.) and 1 640 (C=O amide-I) along with 1 680 (C=O), 1 580 (C—N) and 700 cm⁻¹ (C=O, C—N and C—S—C str. of thiazolidinone moiety respectively). The ¹H nmr spectrum showed singlet at δ 8.50 due to CONH protons, while multiplet in the region δ 7.00–8.00 could be attributed to ArH. A singlet at δ 4.84 could be assigned to ArOCH₂ protons which was found in downfield due to neighbouring oxygen atom. Two singlet at δ 3.56 and 5.30 were due to S—CHAr and S—CH₂CO of thiazolidinone

moiety respectively. Moreover, a singlet in downfield region at δ 11.80 could be due to enolic form (OH) of thiazolidinone moiety (may be possible by transfer of CH_2 proton to adjacent $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group in thiazolidinone moiety).

The thiazolidinone (4; $\text{R}'=\text{CH}_3$) gave the characteristic bands at 1250 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ asym.) and 1690 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ amide-I) alongwith 1690, 1600 and 720 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{N}$ and $\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C}$ str. of thiazolidinone moiety respectively). The ^1H nmr spectrum revealed the presence of a singlet at δ 8.18 (CONH) and a multiplet at δ 5.22 (ArOCH_2). $\text{S}-\text{CHAr}$ gave a signal at δ 4.74. $\text{S}-\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$ moiety of thiazolidinone gave only a singlet (CH_2) at δ 2.96 suggesting the transfer of methane proton to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group, which gave a signal at δ 11.32. This is also confirmed by a band at 3475 cm^{-1} (OH) in the ir spectrum.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening of 4-thiazolidinone derivatives was carried out using cup-plate method⁴ at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus citreus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Marcasane serratia* and fungi *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus niger*.

Activity of the compounds tested was determined by measuring zone of inhibition in mm.

The results obtained from antimicrobial screening showed that most of the compounds are moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi (12–20 mm, zone of inhibition) at a 50 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ concentration which comes under the category of low activity. So data on the microbial activities are not presented.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The structure of the compounds have been established on the basis of their elemental analyses and spectral data. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on XL-100A (100.1 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

***p,p'*-Bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (2):** An aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate (7 ml; 80%) was added to a suspension of *p,p'*-bis(carbomethoxymethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (8.45 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (15 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h and cooled to room temperature. The hydrazide thus separated on cooling was isolated and crystallised from DMF, (6.85 g, 87%), m.p. 228° (Found: C, 48.77; H, 4.57; N, 14.14. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires: C, 48.72; H, 4.60; N, 14.20%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1250 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ asym.), 1145, 1290 ($\text{S}=\text{O}$ asym. and sym. respectively), 3300 (NH or NH_2) and 1680 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); δ (DMSO- d_6) 9.4 (2H, s, $2\times\text{CONH}$), 4.32 (4H, s, $2\times\text{NH}_2$), 4.6 (4H, s, $2\times\text{H}_2\text{COAr}$) and 8.0–6.96 (8H, m, $2\times\text{ArH}$).

***p,p'*-Bis(benzalhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (1):** A mixture of benzaldehyde (2.02 ml, 0.02 mol) and *p,p'*-bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)-diphenyl sulphone (3.94 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol was refluxed in presence of acetic acid (few drops) for 6 h, and the reaction mixture was then poured onto crushed ice. The resulting solid was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (3.88 g, 68%), m.p. 172° (Found: C, 63.12; H, 4.60; N, 6.84. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{S}$ requires: C, 63.14; H, 4.59; N, 9.82%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1250 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ asym.), 1125, 1300 ($\text{S}=\text{O}$ asym. and sym. respectively), 1690 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ amide-I) and 1650 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}=\text{CH}$); δ (DMSO- d_6) 11.36 (2H, s, $2\times\text{NHOC}$, exchangeable with D_2O), 5.13 (4H, s, $2\times\text{H}_2\text{COAr}$), 4.65 (2H, s, $2\times\text{RCH}=\text{N}$) and 8.17–6.75 (18H, m, $4\times\text{ArH}$).

Similarly, other anils (2–20) were prepared by the same method (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF *p,p'*-BIS(SUBSTITUTED BENZALHYDRAZINOCARBONYLMETHOXY) DIPHENYL SULPHONES*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1.	Phenyl	172	68	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4\text{S}$
2.	4-Methylphenyl	238	72	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4\text{S}$
3.	Cinnamyl	198	65	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4\text{S}$
4.	2-Chlorophenyl	232	70	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4\text{SCl}_2$
5.	4-Chlorophenyl	243	76	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4\text{SCl}_2$
6.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	254	66	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4\text{SCl}_4$
7.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	237	62	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4\text{SCl}_4$
8.	2-Methoxyphenyl	238	72	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}$
9.	4-Methoxyphenyl	214	79	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}$
10.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	242	70	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{S}$
11.	3-Methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl	170	60	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{S}$
12.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	236	64	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{S}$
13.	2-Nitrophenyl	220	80	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_6\text{S}$
14.	3-Nitrophenyl	208	78	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_6\text{S}$
15.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	248	59	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}$
16.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	106	65	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}$
17.	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichlorophenyl	174	72	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4\text{SCl}_4$
18.	3-Aminophenyl	177	62	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8\text{N}_6\text{S}$
19.	4-Aminophenyl	140	67	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8\text{N}_6\text{S}$
20.	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	224	60	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_8\text{N}_6\text{S}$

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

***p,p'*-Bis(2-aryl-4-thiazolidinon-3-ylcarbamoylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (Table 1, sl. no. 21):** A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(benzalhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (5.7 g, 0.01 mol), dry benzene (100 ml) and thioglycolic acid (1.73 ml, 0.025 mol) was refluxed for 30 h using Dean and Stark water separator. The reaction mixture was then cooled and excess benzene was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was washed several times with NaHCO_3 solution and water, and crystallised from dioxane-DMF (3:1) solvent, (5.75 g, 80%), m.p. 186° (Found: C, 56.84; H, 4.17; N, 7.73. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_4\text{O}_8\text{S}_2$ requires: C, 56.80; H, 4.20; N, 7.79%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1240 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ asym.), 1145, 1345 ($\text{S}=\text{O}$ asym. and sym. respectively), 1640 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ amide-I), 1680, 1580 and 700 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{N}$ and $\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C}$ str. of thiazolidinone moiety).

respectively); δ (DMSO- d_6) 11.80 (2H, s, 2×OH enolic of thiazolidinones moiety), 8.50 (2H, s, 2×CONH), 7.00–8.00 (18H, m, 4×ArH), 5.30 (4H, s, 2×S–CH₂CO of thiazolidinone), 4.84 (4H, s, 2×ArOCH₃) and 3.56 (2H, s, 2×S–CHAR of thiazolidinone).

Similarly, other 4-thiazolidinones (22–40) were prepared (Table 2, sl. nos. 22–40).

p,p'-Bis(2-aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl-methoxy)diphenyl sulphone (Table 2, sl. no 41): A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(benzalhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (5.7 g, 0.01 mol) and thiolactic acid (2.21 ml, 0.025 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The resulting solid was isolated and crystallised from dioxane–DMF (3:1) solvent, (5.67 g, 76%), m.p. 221° (Found: C, 57.83; H, 4.57; N, 7.46 C₂₆H₂₄N₄O₈S₂ requires: C, 57.88; H, 4.58; N, 7.50%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 250 (C–O–C str., asym.), 1 145, 1 295 (S=O asym. and sym. respectively), 1 690 (C=O amide-I), 1 690, 1 600 and 720 cm⁻¹ (C=O, C–N and C–S–C str. of thiazolidinone moiety respectively); δ (DMSO- d_6) 11.32 (2H, d, 2×OH enolic of thiazolidinone moiety), 8.18 (2H, s, 2×CONH), 6.64–8.00 (18H, m, 4×ArH), 5.22 (4H, s, 2×ArOCH₃), 4.74 (2H, s, 2×S–CHAR of thiazolidinone) and 2.96 (6H, s, 2×S–CHCH₃ of thiazolidinone).

Similarly, other 4-thiazolidinones (42–60) were prepared (Table 2, sl. nos. 42–60).

(Table 2 contd.)

36.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	220	77	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂
37.	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichlorophenyl	166	80	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂
38.	3-Aminophenyl	146	62	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂
39.	4-Aminophenyl	206	69	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂
40.	4-Dimethylamino-phenyl	218	59	C ₂₆ H ₄₀ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂ R'=CH ₃
41.	Phenyl	221	76	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂
42.	4-Methylphenyl	250	80	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂
43.	Cinnamyl	120	56	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂
44.	2-Chlorophenyl	274	79	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂
45.	4-Chlorophenyl	263	85	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂
46.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	279	82	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂ Cl ₄
47.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	248	73	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂ Cl ₄
48.	2-Methoxyphenyl	276	72	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂
49.	4-Methoxyphenyl	217	82	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂
50.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	244	86	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂
51.	3-Methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl	188	68	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂
52.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	254	79	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂
53.	2-Nitrophenyl	240	77	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ N ₆ S ₂
54.	3-Nitrophenyl	270	83	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ N ₆ S ₂
55.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	258	64	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂
56.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	158	73	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂
57.	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichlorophenyl	172	70	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂
58.	3-Aminophenyl	166	60	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂
59.	4-Aminophenyl	178	66	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂
60.	4-Dimethylamino-phenyl	288	74	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF *p,p'*-BIS(2-ARYL-5H/METHYL-4-THIAZOLIDINON-3-YL-CARBAMOYL METHOXY) DIPHENYL SULPHONES*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
				R'=H
21.	Phenyl	186	80	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂
22.	4-Methylphenyl	198	76	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂
23.	Cinnamyl	210	68	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂
24.	2-Chlorophenyl	259	74	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂
25.	4-Chlorophenyl	241	79	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂
26.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	264	82	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂ Cl ₄
27.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	286	79	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₄ S ₂ Cl ₄
28.	2-Methoxyphenyl	268	68	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂
29.	4-Methoxyphenyl	128	76	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂
30.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	244	83	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂
31.	3-Methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl	168	64	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂
32.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	223	66	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂
33.	2-Nitrophenyl	228	86	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ N ₆ S ₂
34.	3-Nitrophenyl	256	81	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ N ₆ S ₂
35.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	251	70	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂

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